

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INSTRUCTIONS ON THE TOPIC OF PRONOUNS IN THE BOOKS TITLED “MASTERING ENGLISH” AND “STRUCTURE AND MEANING IN ENGLISH”

Laylokhon Khabibullaeva

MA TESOL graduate at Webster University in Tashkent

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Annotation: Grammar is an essential part of teaching a foreign language, especially English for elementary level learners. To successfully learn a new language, instructions and explanations on certain grammar topics should be suitable for the language students. This study compares two well-known grammar books: “Mastering English” by Bache & Davidsen-Nielsen (1997) and “Structure and Meaning in English” by Kennedy (2003) by considering their way of expressing the topic “Pronouns”. The purpose of the study is to analyze and determine which book is suitable to teach pronouns to elementary level Uzbek learners.

Keywords: Grammar topics, pronouns, instructions, elementary level, structures.

Annotatsiya: Grammatika chet tilini o'rgatishda, ayniqsa boshlang'ich darajadagi ingliz tili o'rganuvchilari uchun juda muhimdir. Yangi tilni yaxshi o'rganish uchun grammatik mavzular bo'yicha ko'rsatmalar va tushuntirishlar til o'rganuvchilar darajasiga mos bo'lishi kerak. Ushbu tadqiqot "Mastering English" (Bache va Davidsen-Nielsen, 1997) va "Structure and Meaning in English" (Kennedy, 2003) kitoblarini "Olmoshlar" mavzusi bo'yicha taqqoslaydi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi qaysi kitob boshlang'ich darajadagi o'zbek o'rganuvchilarga olmoshlarni o'rgatishda yaxshiroq ekanligini aniqlashdir.

Tayanch so'zlar: Grammatik mavzular, olmoshlar, ko'rsatmalar, boshlang'ich daraja, strukturalar

Pronouns are a fundamental part of a language, as they help speakers to avoid repetitions and redundancy. However, most learners find English pronouns difficult to learn and use as they have similar forms and functions. In order to find a well-planned explanation of the topic “Pronouns”, the teacher should be able to consider students’ language levels, interests and cognitive abilities as well. This study focuses on the information about two different books’ quality, way of explaining the topic, terms used, and the suitability of the given examples.

Methodology

Participant

The participants of this study are 11 freshmen students who are aged between 18-22 at Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature. According to the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR), they are at an elementary (A2) level. In terms of their grammar knowledge, they have a basic understanding of the rules and structures but have difficulties using them in their speeches.

The students are native speakers of Uzbek, which is widely spoken there as their first language (L1). They probably have different socioeconomic origins, but they have in common shared educational experience and cultural background.

They are not very confident in their use of English vocabulary and grammar rules because they are just starting out. Although they may have previously studied some English in school, they are still getting to know the language. While some students prefer it when teachers teach grammar in a more implicit manner, others prefer it when teachers provide examples and a clear explanation of grammar rules.

It's important to use mixed methods to help them improve their language levels. We usually have lessons where we discuss grammar rules and do exercises, but we can also practice using English in real-life situations, like having discussions or doing role-plays. As they have a clear understanding of a language structure and system, they can easily analyze and differentiate certain rules in English, which leads to faster learning of grammar.

Materials

I used e-versions of the books:

1. *Mastering English: an advanced grammar for non-native and native speakers* by Bache & Davidsen-Nielsen (1997)
2. *Structure and meaning in English* by Kennedy (2003)

Procedure:

I analyzed the sections on pronouns in both books. While analyzing, I evaluated the explanations, exercises, and examples provided. After that, I implemented lessons based on each book with the target learners and gathered feedback.

Grammar Topic Exploration

Pronouns in "Mastering English" describes pronouns using the term "pronominals" and provides detailed, theoretical explanations of pronoun use, including syntax and reference in clauses. Furthermore, it presents complex structures, making it more suited for advanced learners.

Pronouns in "Structure and Meaning in English" offer simpler explanations, using charts and tables to aid comprehension. It includes practical exercises and contextual examples, which are more accessible to A2-level learners.

Results and Discussions

While observing the topic "Pronouns" from the books "Structure and Meaning in English" by Kennedy (2003) and «Mastering English: an advanced grammar for non-native and native speakers » by Bache & Davidsen-Nielsen (1997), I realized some similarities and distinct features of them.

Although both books have used the term "Pronouns", in the book «Mastering English» there is a term "Pronominals" used to generalize the topic. According to this book, "Pronominals are pronouns or pronouns groups". In terms of sub-groups of pronouns, the same terms and divisions have been used by two authors.

The feature that makes Kennedy(2003)'s book different from Bache & Davidsen-Nielsen (1997)'s work is that he provided special exercises and tasks for each unit and at the end of the themes there are several topics to discuss to check understanding.

Another important point about the book "Structure and meaning in English", it includes example sentences that are simple and easy to understand. Moreover, the authors presented the topic "Pronoun" in terms of person, gender, case and number. But Bache & Davidsen-Nielsen (1997) described it more widely, especially by considering its syntax, reference and usage features. Furthermore, they also provided information about the use of pronouns in clauses, and their differences in meaning.

One more significant distinction in their work is that they explained each sub-group and each pronoun in a thorough and detailed way, by giving examples for each. Their work seems a bit complicated and theoretical, as main parts are presented in a paragraph format. Unlike their work, Kennedy (2003) used graphs and tables to express ideas, which makes his work more comprehensible and easy to follow.

Overall, differences between the two books might include how deeply they explain pronouns, how they organize their content, the examples they use, which aspects of pronouns they focus on, and who they're written for. "Structure and Meaning in English" covers common topics and can be for both native and non-native speakers, while " Mastering English: an Advanced Grammar for Non-native and Native Speakers " might focus on more theoretical aspects of

pronouns. As the learner are just at A2 level, I would prefer using “Structure and Meaning in English” by Kennedy(1997).

Conclusion

For EFL students at an elementary level, selecting grammar materials that balance theoretical knowledge with practical exercises is crucial. “Structure and Meaning in English” is the more effective resource for teaching pronouns, as it aligns better with the learning needs of A2 learners.

Future research could involve a larger sample of students and cover additional grammar topics to further ensure these findings.

References:

1. Bache, C., & Davidsen-Nielsen, N. (1997). Mastering English: an advanced grammar for non-native and native speakers. Mouten de Gruyter
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